

**Deliverable
D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-
WP4.2
Report on the prevalence of
oocyst-derived infections in
humans and animals**

**Workpackage 4 of
JRP22-FBZ4.1-
TOXOSOURCES**

Responsible Partners:
ISS, RKI, SSI

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DELIVERABLE

D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.2

REPORT ON THE PREVALENCE OF OOCYST-DERIVED INFECTIONS IN HUMANS AND ANIMALS

TOXOSOURCES – PROJECT

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-toxosources/>);

Work Package:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4 Serology method based on novel antigens to discriminate *T. gondii* infections acquired from oocysts

Task:

JRP22-WP4-T3 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-derived *T. gondii* infections in animals and humans

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TOXOSOURCES addresses the research question – **What are the relative contributions of the different sources of *T. gondii* infection?** – by using several multidisciplinary approaches and novel and improved methods to yield robust estimates that can inform risk management and policy makers.

TOXOSOURCES WP4 explores serology for source-attribution of *T. gondii* infections.

Objectives of TOXOSOURCES WP4:

- ✓ To identify *T. gondii* antigens with source-attributing potential (proteins of interest, POIs)
- ✓ To explore serological methods that discriminate oocyst- from tissue cyst-driven infections
- ✓ To estimate the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in humans and animals

The task TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T3 aimed to improve our understanding on *T. gondii* oocyst transmission to domestic animals and game animals used for human consumption as well as humans in Europe. Different management and breeding systems are known to affect the prevalence of *T. gondii* in animals, and seroprevalence differs substantially by geographical region in game animals (TOXOSOURCES WP2). Likewise, *T. gondii* prevalence in humans is affected by factors including geographical setting and consumption habits (TOXOSOURCES WP2).

The plans for the task included also conducting a ring trial on the serology method developed in WP4 and test the robustness of possible stage-specific antigens identified by using panels of sera, in case antigens suitable for these would be identified by TOXOSOURCES WP4-T1 and WP4T2. The objective of TOXOSOURCES-WP4 was ambitious and identified as high-risk-high-gain. The rigorous pipeline designed and followed for the serological tool development, together with an exhaustive selection of proteins of interest and control sera, produced rigorous results that at present have not identified a suitable antigen that would be ready for the final assay validation steps, including interlaboratory ring trial and evaluation of diagnostic performance using field samples (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Workflow to develop an assay to differentiate oocyst-driven infections vs. tissue cyst-driven infections from a One Health perspective and according to OIE guidelines (Álvarez-García et al., 2021).

The work done in WP4-T3 successfully produced concrete plans for final assay validation steps, new collaborations, and contributions to literature reviews in TOXOSOURCES WP2. WP4-T3 made concrete plans that are ready to be taken to use. The consortium gathered experience in designing and conducting ring trials (conducted in WP3 and WP5). The consortium has access to suitable sera for exploring the relative prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in several animal species, and the consortium established collaborations with colleagues in South-America, where several waterborne toxoplasmosis outbreaks have occurred, for access to human samples. As sending samples from human subjects from another continent to Europe is challenging, the collaboration in the coming years is expected to rather focus on transfer of methodology and expertise.

The work on stage-specific serology continues, and in the meantime, the multidisciplinary approach of TOXOSOURCES can provide reflections and clues on the relative importance of oocyst-derived infections.

Direct detection of DNA of the parasite, indicating oocyst contamination, on ready-to-eat fresh produce (WP3), highlights the risk of oocyst-derived infections, and was taken into account in the modelling work (WP2).

Most livestock species are fed herbivorous diets, and therefore oocysts are their likely source of infection. Thus, the meatborne pathway of human infections, from ingesting undercooked meat of infected domestic animals, can be seen as a further step from the environmental pathway. Exemplified by another foodborne zoonotic parasite genus *Trichinella*, infections acquired by carnivorous animals can however also occur among animals considered as herbivores.

The prevalence of *T. gondii* infections in the definitive hosts felids can provide an indication of the level of environmental contamination with oocysts. Due to the environmental contamination, the risk of acquiring *T. gondii* infection is higher in animals raised outdoors than in animals kept indoors. Herbivorous wildlife host species can be useful indicator species of the environmental contamination with oocysts.

REFERENCES

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